

1 Hydrostatic pressure and temperature affect the tolerance of the free-living marine
2 nematode *Halomonhystera disjuncta* to acute copper exposure

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10 Abstract

11 Potential deep-sea mineral extraction poses new challenges for ecotoxicological research
12 since little is known about effects of abiotic conditions present in the deep sea on the toxicity
13 of heavy metals. Due to the difficulty of collecting and maintaining deep-sea organisms alive,
14 a first step would be to understand the effects of high hydrostatic pressure and low
15 temperatures on heavy metal toxicity using shallow-water relatives of deep-sea species.
16 Here, we present the results of acute copper toxicity tests on the free-living shallow-water
17 marine nematode *Halomonhystera disjuncta*, which has close phylogenetic and ecological
18 links to the bathyal species *Halomonhystera hermesii*. Copper toxicity was assessed using a
19 semi-liquid gellan gum medium at two levels of hydrostatic pressure (0.1 MPa and 10 MPa)
20 and temperature (10 °C and 20 °C) in a fully crossed design. Mortality of nematodes in each
21 treatment was assessed at 4 time intervals (24 and 48 h for all experiments and additionally
22 72 and 96 h for experiments run at 10 °C). LC₅₀ values ranged between 0.561 and 1.864 mg
23 Cu²⁺ L⁻¹ and showed a decreasing trend with incubation time. Exposure to high hydrostatic
24 pressure significantly increased sensitivity of nematodes to copper, whereas lower
25 temperature resulted in an apparent increased copper tolerance, possibly as a result of a
26 slower metabolism under low temperatures. These results indicate that hydrostatic pressure
27 and temperature significantly affect metal toxicity and therefore need to be considered in
28 toxicity assessments for deep-sea species. Any application of pollution limits derived from
29 studies of shallow-water species to the deep-sea mining context must be done cautiously,
30 with consideration of the effects of both stressors.

31 Keywords: Hydrostatic pressure; LC₅₀; Copper toxicity; *Halomonhystera disjuncta*; Deep-sea
32 mining; Gellan Gum

33 1. Introduction

34 Economically valuable mineral deposits can be found in a variety of deep-sea habitats such
35 as abyssal plains (polymetallic nodules and deep-sea muds), active and extinct hydrothermal
36 vents (seafloor massive sulphides) or seamounts (ferromanganese crusts) (Hein et al., 2013;
37 Petersen et al., 2016; Sterk and Stein, 2015). The extraction of these mineral deposits may
38 cause significant disturbances of these remote and ecologically valuable habitats,
39 threatening their biological communities (Vanreusel et al., 2016). Despite significant
40 international attention, ecosystems of these areas are poorly studied and mechanisms of
41 resilience and recovery of the benthic fauna are largely unknown (Gollner et al., 2017;
42 Wedding et al., 2015). One major concern is the mobilization and release of elevated
43 concentrations of potentially toxic elements during extraction, transport in riser systems, or
44 after processing of the minerals (e.g. the release of extraction water or tailings to the water
45 column) (Boschen et al., 2013; Koschinsky et al., 2001a, 2001b; Thiel, 2001). Heavy metal
46 concentrations are usually higher within marine sediments than the overlying water column
47 as heavy metals bind to small particles, organic matter and different hydroxides
48 (Pempkowiak et al., 1999). Infaunal organisms are, therefore, particularly vulnerable to metal
49 exposure if conditions in sediment or surrounding seawater change (e.g. pH, oxygen
50 saturation) and bioavailability of those metals increases. The development of appropriate
51 measures to identify risk requires knowledge of the impacts of heavy metal contamination on
52 deep-sea benthic organisms. However, the acquisition and maintenance of deep-sea
53 organisms is challenging, hampering their use in controlled laboratory experiments. As a first
54 step towards understanding heavy metal toxicity in the deep sea researchers are advised to
55 uncover the effects of abiotic factors such as high hydrostatic pressure and low temperatures
56 on the sensitivity of marine species (Mestre et al., 2014). These two factors play major roles
57 in determining the distribution of marine organisms (Brown and Thatje, 2011; Clarke, 2003;
58 Pörtner, 2002; Pradillon and Gaill, 2007). Knowledge of pressure and temperature effects on
59 metal toxicity would help us to better understand underlying mechanisms and possibly
60 predict potential toxic effects in deep-sea species.

61 Copper is a trace element that is essential to the health of most organisms (Mertz, 1981). It
62 plays a role in multiple physiological pathways (e.g. in regulating oxidative stress), as a co-
63 factor of several enzymes or structural components and is also associated with biological
64 processes such as responses to hypoxia (Karlin and Tyeklár, 2012; Scheiber et al., 2013).
65 However, an excess of copper can induce severe toxicity leading to metabolic dysfunction
66 and ultimately to the death of an organism (Gaetke and Chow, 2003; Scheiber et al., 2013).
67 Deep-sea minerals contain relatively high concentrations of copper (Hein et al., 2013) and it
68 has been demonstrated that the potential for copper leaching from deep-sea minerals such

69 as chalcopyrite is high (Fallon et al., 2017; Knight and Roberts, 2016). However, Simpson
70 and Spadaro (2016) have recently reported limited toxicity of chalcopyrite-induced, copper-
71 associated mortality in bivalves and amphipods. The relative high importance of copper in
72 deep-sea mineral extraction and its important role in animal physiology support the need to
73 explore the effects of hydrostatic pressure and temperature on copper toxicity.

74 Intermediate in size between micro- and macrofauna, metazoan meiobenthos play a major
75 role in the benthic ecosystem as an important component of the benthic food-web, but also
76 through facilitating mineralization and nutrient turnover (Bonaglia et al., 2014; Coull, 1999;
77 Moens et al., 2013). Nematodes are the dominant taxon within this group of organisms and
78 their short life span and high fecundity also make them suitable for laboratory experiments
79 and short-term ecotoxicological research in particular (Beyrem et al., 2011; Kennedy and
80 Jacoby, 1999). The tolerance of nematodes to metal toxicity, hypoxia and changing
81 environmental conditions can be very variable and species dependent (Bongers and Ferris,
82 1999; Gyedu-Ababio and Baird, 2006). *Halomonhystera disjuncta* is a free-living,
83 bacterivorous shallow-water marine nematode which is known for its tolerance to
84 temperature changes and high concentrations of heavy metals (Vranken et al., 1989, 1988,
85 1985, 1984). The intertidal, cryptic species *Halomonhystera disjuncta* GD1 (Derycke et al.,
86 2007) is phylogenetically closely related to the species *H. hermesii* (Tchesunov et al., 2014)
87 which inhabits cold-seep ecosystems in the deep sea, e.g. the Nyegga pockmark at 730 m
88 on the Nordic Norwegian margin and the Håkon Mosby mud volcano at 1280 m depth in the
89 Barents Sea (Van Campenhout et al., 2015, 2013; Van Gaeve et al., 2006). Interestingly, *H.*
90 *disjuncta* GD1 also shows higher tolerance towards bathyal seep conditions (high sulphide
91 concentrations, low temperature) than other species in the cryptic species complex (Van
92 Campenhout et al., 2014). The close phylogenetic relationship and *H. disjuncta* GD1's
93 environmental tolerances suggest that *H. disjuncta* and *H. hermesii* share a recent common
94 ancestor (Van Campenhout et al., 2015, 2014, 2013), making *H. disjuncta* a relevant species
95 with which to investigate the effects of bathyal environmental conditions on copper toxicity.

96 In this study, we performed the first acute copper toxicity tests on the free-living marine
97 nematode *H. disjuncta* incorporating different hydrostatic pressure and temperature regimes.
98 The use of gellan gum as a medium for nematode toxicity testing has been described by
99 Brinke et al. (2011) and was chosen for this study to facilitate the use of pressure chambers
100 under the exclusion of air cavities. In comparison to water, gellan gum provides the
101 advantage that the sediment dwelling nematodes are still able to move through the medium
102 by body undulations but with lower activity and stress than would result from constant
103 swimming in water. We investigated the acute effects of bathyal pressure experienced by *H.*
104 *hermesii* on copper toxicity in *H. disjuncta* by including two pressures (0.1 MPa= surface

105 pressure, and 10 MPa \approx 1000 m water depth) and two temperatures (20°C and 10°C). Here,
106 20°C represents a standard temperature for toxicity testing that has been applied in previous
107 acute toxicity studies on marine nematodes including *H. disjuncta* (Austen and McEvoy,
108 1997; Vranken et al., 1984; Vranken and Heip, 1986) whereas 10 °C is at the lower end of
109 the species optimal temperature range whilst allowing normal growth and development (Van
110 Campenhout et al., 2014). With this study we aim to investigate 1) the effect of high
111 hydrostatic pressure on the survival of a shallow-water nematode and 2) the extent to which
112 temperature and hydrostatic pressure affect copper toxicity in the shallow-water nematode.

113 2. Material and Methods

114 2.1. Nematode cultures

115 Monospecific cultures of *H. disjuncta* cryptic species GD1 were cultivated at 16 °C on petri
116 dishes filled with 0.8 % nutrient:bacto agar in a ratio of 1:7 prepared in artificial seawater
117 (Moens and Vincx, 1998) with a salinity of 25. The cultures were incubated at the respective
118 experimental temperature one week prior to the experiment. An excess of frozen-and-thawed
119 *Escherichia coli* K12 were added as a food source. A full description of species acquisition
120 for the cultures is given in Van Campenhout et al. (2014).

121 2.2. Experimental setup

122 Nematodes of the species *H. disjuncta* GD1 were exposed to five different copper (Cu^{2+})
123 concentrations at two different temperatures (10 °C and 20 °C) and two different pressures
124 (0.1 MPa and 10 MPa) for 2 time intervals (24 h, 48 h) with 3 replicates per time interval and
125 treatment. In addition, experiments at 10 °C were also run for 72 h and 96 h. Selection of
126 dissolved copper concentrations at 10 °C (0, 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 6 mg Cu^{2+} L⁻¹) and 20 °C (0, 0.2,
127 0.5, 1, 2, 5 mg Cu^{2+} L⁻¹) were based on preliminary ranging experiments at atmospheric
128 pressure. Survival was the chosen endpoint.

129 Screw top vials of 5 mL volume with a rubber septum were half filled with Cu^{2+} -contaminated
130 gellan gum and 20 adult and preadult nematodes were placed in the vials. The vials were
131 then filled up with the Cu^{2+} -contaminated gellan gum medium and closed, ensuring that no
132 air bubbles were trapped. One vial (empty control) without nematodes was added to each
133 replicate measurement. Vials were placed in a pressure vessel, acutely pressurised, and
134 incubated at the respective pressure and temperature for the respective time intervals (24,
135 48, 72 and 96 hours). A detailed description of the pressure vessels can be found in Mestre
136 et al. (2009). Vials of all treatments, including those at surface pressure, were placed in
137 pressure vessels to avoid any experimental artefacts arising from enclosure in the pressure
138 vessel.

139 The semi-liquid gellan gum medium was made with 1.5 g L⁻¹ gelrite (Merck & Co., Kelco
140 Division) solution prepared in MilliQ water and artificial seawater (Moens and Vincx, 1998)
141 with a salinity of 34. The two components were autoclaved and the gellan gum solution was
142 slowly added to the seawater in a 1:3 ratio under continuous stirring to obtain the required
143 fluidity and salinity of 25. Sufficient volumes of medium were spiked with different dissolved
144 copper (Cu²⁺) concentrations by adding the appropriate amount of CuSO₄ stock solution to
145 the medium under continuous stirring for ~2 minutes. The stock solution was composed of
146 0.10155 g CuSO₄ and 250 mL MilliQ water resulting in a dissolved Cu²⁺ concentration of
147 259.66 mg L⁻¹.

148 At the end of each experiment, hydrostatic pressure vessels were immediately depressurised
149 and oxygen levels in the middle of the vials were measured with an oxygen optode
150 connected to a PreSens Microx TX3 array. Nematode mortality was assessed by observing
151 movement through a stereo-microscope and/or response to physical stimulation with a
152 needle.

153 Unavoidable bacterial contamination of the medium and nematode respiration led to a
154 decrease of oxygen concentrations in the vials, especially at high temperatures. Based on
155 the oxygen measurements we adjusted our experimental setup and only conducted 24 h and
156 48 h treatments at 20 °C, however, these particular treatment combinations were repeated
157 once with a full set of 3 replicates. Furthermore, data analysis was adjusted by removing
158 treatments where very low oxygen concentrations (<5 %) persisted in most vials at low
159 copper concentrations in combination with an increased mortality of animals in those vials
160 (Tab. S1). Potential oxygen-associated background mortality at zero copper concentration
161 was accounted for in the data analysis. Oxygen deficiency and mortality occurred in all
162 replicates of the following treatments: 20 °C, 0.1 MPa, 24 h (first measurement); 20 °C, 10
163 MPa, 24 h (first measurement); 20 °C, 0.1 MPa, 48 h (second measurement) and 20 °C, 10
164 MPa, 48 h (second measurement)(Tab. S1). Therefore, one set of replicates at each
165 pressure at 24 and 48 h was retained in the analysis.

166 *2.3. Data analysis*

167 LC₅₀ values and their confidence intervals were estimated from dose response curves based
168 on the three replicates of each treatment, fitted with a binomial regression using a probit link
169 and adjusting for background mortality as explained by Proctor et al. (2017). The models of
170 the dose-response curves were then compared by Analysis of Deviance (chi-squared) which
171 allows comparison of generalized linear models comparable to variance testing in ANOVA
172 (Nelder and Wedderburn, 1972). Additionally, dose-response curves were fitted with the very
173 similar log-normal function with fixed upper (1) and lower (0) limits (LN.2) using the *drc*
174 package. This package allows for comprehensive visualization of the models. All data were

175 analysed with the statistical software R version 3.4.0 Patched (R Core Team, 2013) and
 176 RStudio version 1.0.136 (RStudio Team, 2015) using the packages *LC50* (Proctor and
 177 Wotherspoon, 2015) and *drc* (Ritz et al., 2015). A significance level of $\alpha=0.05$ was chosen for
 178 all tests.

179 3. Results

180 At the end of each experiment, nematode behaviour and motility in treatments without Cu^{2+}
 181 contamination appeared unaffected by compression and decompression. Surviving animals
 182 from high pressure treatments appeared and behaved similarly to those under atmospheric
 183 pressure.

184 LC_{50} values ranged between $0.561 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (10 MPa, 10 °C after 72 h) and 1.864mg L^{-1} (0.1
 185 MPa, 10 °C, after 24 h) and showed a decreasing trend with incubation time (Fig. 1).
 186 Pressure and temperature significantly affected nematode sensitivity towards copper at the
 187 24 h and 48 h time intervals, without an interaction effect (Tab. S2): nematode sensitivity in
 188 terms of LC_{50} was greater at 10 MPa than at 0.1 MPa and was greater at 20 °C than at 10 °C
 189 (Fig. 1). The negative effect of high pressure was still visible after 72 h of incubation but not
 190 at 96 h (Tab. 1).

191 **Table 1** Results of the Analysis of Deviance comparing dose-response models of varying factors pressure (0.1 and 10 MPa)
 192 and temperature (10 and 20 °C). DF= degrees of freedom, NULL= null model (no variables included), Pr(>Chi)= probability of
 193 the model being different from the null model.

		DF	Deviance	Residual DF	Residual Deviance	Pr (>Chi)	
24 h	NULL			63	233.8		
	Temperature	1	66.838	62	166.96	2.95E-16	***
	Pressure	1	24.956	61	142	5.87E-07	***
	Temperature*Pressure	1	0.408	60	141.6	0.5231	
48 h	NULL			63	156.3		
	Temperature	1	30.683	62	125.62	3.04E-08	***
	Pressure	1	12.564	61	113.05	3.93E-04	***
	Temperature*Pressure	1	0	60	113.06	1	
72 h	NULL			31	143.838		
	Pressure	1	79.983	30	63.855	2.20E-16	***
96 h	NULL			31	55.105		
	Pressure	1	1.1235	30	53.982	0.2892	

*** Significant at the $p \leq 0.001$ probability level

194

195

196 **Figure 1** Mean LC₅₀ values with upper and lower confidence intervals (error bars) for all experiments conducted in a fully
 197 crossed design with two varying factors (temperature and pressure), N=3.

198 In addition to differences in the LC₅₀, the slope of the dose-response curve was slightly
 199 flattened when high hydrostatic pressure was applied (Fig 2., Tab. S2). A flattened slope
 200 indicates that the range of concentrations that is harmful for part of the population is larger
 201 whereas a steep slope is an indication for a sharp threshold level where passing the
 202 threshold leads to a strong increase in toxicity producing lower survival rates.

203

204 **Figure 2** Dose-response curves (log-normal models) of the copper toxicity tests at differing pressure (0.1 and 10 MPa) and
 205 temperature (10 and 20 °C) for 4 different time intervals. Symbols represent the individual replicate measurements of nematode
 206 survival.

207 4. Discussion

208 4.1. Effects of hydrostatic pressure

209 Hydrostatic pressure strongly determines the depth distribution of marine species (Brown
210 and Thatje, 2014). This is a result of evolutionary adaptation of marine organisms to the
211 adverse effects of high hydrostatic pressure on molecular interactions, e.g. with regard to
212 electrochemical and hydrophobic interactions in biological systems (Brown and Thatje, 2014;
213 Pradillon and Gaill, 2007). Nevertheless, shallow-water marine invertebrates seem to have a
214 wider tolerance to increased hydrostatic pressure than might be predicted *a priori* (Brown
215 and Thatje, 2014; Mestre et al., 2013, 2009; Smith et al., 2015) and are able to increase their
216 tolerance after a short acclimation period (New et al., 2014). Similarly, in this study, mortality
217 and activity of *H. disjuncta* in treatments without Cu²⁺ contamination remained unaffected by
218 elevated pressure. Therefore, mortality associated with pressurization and depressurization
219 was not an interfering factor in the assessment of copper toxicity. However, while the
220 nematodes were tolerant in the short-term, negative effects of high hydrostatic pressure on
221 the nematodes may arise with longer exposures.

222 In this study, high hydrostatic pressure reduced the tolerance of *H. disjuncta* to copper
223 exposure at both 10 and 20 °C, as evidenced by lower LC₅₀ values and a flattened slope
224 compared to surface pressure (Fig. 2). The flattened slope of the dose-response curves at
225 high hydrostatic pressure suggests that a wider range of concentrations adversely affects
226 part of the population. Therefore, even low copper concentrations led to a weakening of the
227 nematodes and mortality of several individuals at 10 MPa. Interestingly, the effect of
228 pressure was not evident after an incubation time of 96 h which may be caused by interfering
229 factors such as starvation, reducing the organisms' tolerance to additional stress. Research
230 has indicated that starvation effects can become evident after 72-120 h in laboratory
231 experiments with marine nematodes (Ott and Schiemer, 1973; Wieser et al., 1974).

232 Previous research on copper uptake in nematodes has found a strong association of
233 increased amounts of copper concentrations in the cuticle and hypodermis, supporting an
234 uptake via the body wall rather than the digestive tract (Howell, 1983; Savoly et al., 2013).
235 Changes in hydrostatic pressure lead to a shift in biochemical reaction rates and in the
236 fluidity of membranes (Brown and Thatje, 2014; Pradillon and Gaill, 2007) which may in turn
237 affect uptake rates of copper from the environment. Copper toxicity is mainly caused by
238 accumulation of oxidative damage resulting from reactive oxygen species in the cells, and
239 organisms may respond to this by enhancing antioxidant enzyme expression (Song et al.,
240 2014). This, however, will increase basal metabolic rate and may have consequences for the
241 energy allocation of the organisms (Sokolova and Lannig, 2008).

242 Brown et al. (2017a) assessed the effects of low temperature and high hydrostatic pressure
243 on acute (96 h) lethal and sublethal (respiration rate, antioxidant enzyme activity) copper and
244 cadmium toxicity in the shallow-water shrimp *Palaemon varians*. In this study the researchers
245 report that oxygen consumption and antioxidant enzyme activity (superoxide dismutase,
246 glutathione peroxidase) were significantly increased at lower copper concentrations when a
247 pressure of 10 MPa was applied ($100 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) than when at surface pressure ($1000 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$).
248 The exact mechanisms of the effect that pressure has on copper toxicity (e.g. enhanced
249 copper uptake through membranes, inhibition of gene expression) still remain to be
250 investigated, but the results of Brown et al. (2017a) suggest that enzyme expression and
251 activity were not suppressed by increased hydrostatic pressure.

252 Deep-sea organisms have been shown to possess a series of adaptations to counteract the
253 negative effects of hydrostatic pressure on their metabolism (Pradillon and Gaill, 2007;
254 Somero, 2003; Yancey et al., 2004). Nevertheless, it remains to be investigated if these
255 adaptations also enable them to counteract the negative effect of pressure on copper toxicity.
256 This may be answered once our mechanistic understanding of copper toxicity in marine
257 invertebrates and, more specifically in deep-sea invertebrates, improves.

258 *4.2. Effects of temperature*

259 Temperature also affected copper tolerance in *H. disjuncta* and survival of nematodes was
260 higher at 10 °C than at 20 °C. *H. disjuncta*'s optimal growth temperature occurs at
261 approximately 16 °C, but most life history traits do not vary considerably when temperature is
262 reduced to 10 °C (Van Campenhout et al., 2014). Therefore, a temperature of 10 °C can be
263 considered to lie within the species' thermal window. The metabolism of an organism is an
264 interplay of different biochemical reactions performed by multiple enzymes (Brown et al.,
265 2004). These metabolic reactions obey the laws of thermodynamics and increase
266 exponentially with increasing temperatures inside temperature ranges of normal activity
267 (Brown et al., 2004; Clarke and Fraser, 2004). Therefore, the higher tolerance of *H. disjuncta*
268 towards copper at 10 °C compared to 20 °C may be attributed to a slower metabolism at low
269 temperatures leading to a decreased copper uptake, which delays reaching lethal systemic
270 metal concentration. This is consistent with previous research stating that in most ectotherms
271 (80% of N=118 investigated species) an increased temperature enhanced metal toxicity in
272 terms of mortality and uptake (Sokolova and Lannig, 2008; and references therein). Indeed,
273 chromium toxicity in *H. disjuncta* was increased when temperature was high (22 °C)
274 compared to optimal temperature (17 °C) and mortality was reduced at low temperature (12
275 °C) (Vranken et al., 1989).

276 Although deep-sea animals have adapted to very stable and low temperatures (typically 4
277 °C), enzymatic reactions and, consequently, metabolic rate of stenothermal species living at

278 <8 °C is lower compared to eurythermal organisms (Pörtner, 2002). Therefore, the observed
279 lower, acute effects of copper toxicity at low temperature may be similar in deep-sea
280 organisms. However, additional stress responses induced by copper exposure at low,
281 sublethal concentrations may increase basal metabolic maintenance and reduce the amount
282 of energy available for other functions, reducing the organisms' fitness (Brown et al., 2017a;
283 Sokolova et al., 2012). This may especially be of relevance in the food and energy limited
284 abyssal deep sea (Smith et al., 2008). Chronic effects considerably differ from acute
285 exposures and sublethal copper concentrations have been shown to substantially affect life-
286 cycle characteristics (Bechmann, 1994; Kwok et al., 2008). This, in turn, may have unknown
287 consequences for ecosystem functioning and the assessment of chronic toxicity effects
288 should, therefore, be considered in future studies.

289 Temperature and hydrostatic pressure have antagonistic properties with regard to kinetics
290 and equilibria in biological systems e.g. as pressure increases, it reduces the flexibility of
291 lipids and nucleic acids while the opposite is true for temperature increases (Pradillon and
292 Gaill, 2007 and citations therein). However, the results of this study indicate that pressure
293 and temperature act in different ways on the sensitivity of *H. disjuncta* to copper since a
294 simultaneous increase in both, pressure and temperature lead to an increase in copper
295 sensitivity.

296 4.3. Conclusion

297 Our research shows that increased hydrostatic pressure and temperature reduce the
298 sensitivity of *H. disjuncta* to acute copper exposure in terms of mortality. An integrative
299 approach of laboratory experiments using shallow-water species under controlled conditions
300 in combination with *in situ* deep-sea experiments using related species is, therefore, crucial
301 to fully understand ecotoxicology in the deep sea (Brown et al., 2017b). Nevertheless, the
302 use of shallow-water species helps to elucidate general mechanisms of both factors on
303 copper toxicity in marine nematodes.

304 As an acute toxicity assessment with only one toxicant tested, these results are not intended
305 to assess the specific risks of deep-sea mineral extraction, but they provide evidence for
306 effects of hydrostatic pressure and temperature on copper toxicity that need to be considered
307 in environmental risk assessment. *In situ* studies including realistic multiple metal exposures
308 are needed to produce environmentally relevant data and enable proper risk assessment.
309 Furthermore, experiments with longer exposures would enable investigations of effects of
310 chronic exposures to toxicants, which may pose greater risks for organisms in the long term
311 and which cannot be assessed in acute toxicity studies (Freitas and Rocha, 2014).

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323 References

- 324 Austen, M.C., McEvoy, A.J., 1997. The use of offshore meiobenthic communities in
325 laboratory microcosm experiments: response to heavy metal contamination. *J.*
326 *Exp. Mar. Biol. Ecol.* 211, 247–261.
- 327 Bechmann, R.K., 1994. Use of life tables and LC50 tests to evaluate chronic and
328 acute toxicity effects of copper on the marine copepod *Tisbe furcata* (Baird).
329 *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 13, 1509–1517. doi:10.1002/etc.5620130913
- 330 Beyrem, H., Boufahja, F., Hedfi, A., Essid, N., Aïssa, P., Mahmoudi, E., 2011.
331 Laboratory study on individual and combined effects of cobalt-and zinc-spiked
332 sediment on meiobenthic nematodes. *Biol. Trace Elem. Res.* 144, 790–803.
- 333 Bonaglia, S., Nascimento, F.J.A., Bartoli, M., Klawonn, I., Brüchert, V., 2014.
334 Meiofauna increases bacterial denitrification in marine sediments. *Nat.*
335 *Commun.* 5. doi:10.1038/ncomms6133
- 336 Bongers, T., Ferris, H., 1999. Nematode community structure as a bioindicator in
337 environmental monitoring. *Trends Ecol. Evol.* 14, 224–228.
- 338 Boschen, R.E., Rowden, A.A., Clark, M.R., Gardner, J.P.A., 2013. Mining of deep-
339 sea seafloor massive sulfides: A review of the deposits, their benthic
340 communities, impacts from mining, regulatory frameworks and management
341 strategies. *Ocean Coast. Manag.* 84, 54–67.
342 doi:10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2013.07.005
- 343 Brinke, M., Heininger, P., Traunspurger, W., 2011. A semi-fluid gellan gum medium
344 improves nematode toxicity testing. *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 74, 1824–1831.
345 doi:10.1016/j.ecoenv.2011.07.007
- 346 Brown, A., Thatje, S., 2014. Explaining bathymetric diversity patterns in marine
347 benthic invertebrates and demersal fishes: physiological contributions to
348 adaptation of life at depth. *Biol. Rev.* 89, 406–426. doi:10.1111/brv.12061
- 349 Brown, A., Thatje, S., 2011. Respiratory response of the deep-sea amphipod
350 *Stephonyx biscayensis* indicates bathymetric range limitation by temperature
351 and hydrostatic pressure. *PloS One* 6, e28562.
- 352 Brown, A., Thatje, S., Hauton, C., 2017a. The effects of temperature and hydrostatic
353 pressure on metal toxicity: Insights into toxicity in the deep sea. *Environ. Sci.*
354 *Technol.* doi:10.1021/acs.est.7b02988
- 355 Brown, A., Wright, R., Mevenkamp, L., Hauton, C., 2017b. A comparative
356 experimental approach to ecotoxicology in shallow-water and deep-sea

357 holothurians suggests similar behavioural responses. *Aquat. Toxicol.*
358 doi:10.1016/j.aquatox.2017.06.028

359 Brown, J.H., Gillooly, J.F., Allen, A.P., Savage, V.M., West, G.B., 2004. Toward a
360 metabolic theory of ecology. *Ecology* 85, 1771–1789. doi:10.1890/03-9000

361 Clarke, A., 2003. Costs and consequences of evolutionary temperature adaptation.
362 *Trends Ecol. Evol.* 18, 573–581. doi:10.1016/j.tree.2003.08.007

363 Clarke, A., Fraser, K.P.P., 2004. Why does metabolism scale with temperature?
364 *Funct. Ecol.* 18, 243–251. doi:10.1111/j.0269-8463.2004.00841.x

365 Coull, B.C., 1999. Role of meiofauna in estuarine soft-bottom habitats. *Aust. J. Ecol.*
366 24, 327–343. doi:10.1046/j.1442-9993.1999.00979.x

367 Derycke, S., Backeljau, T., Vlaeminck, C., Vierstraete, A., Vanfleteren, J., Vincx, M.,
368 Moens, T., 2007. Spatiotemporal analysis of population genetic structure in
369 *Geomonhystera disjuncta* (Nematoda, Monhysteridae) reveals high levels of
370 molecular diversity. *Mar. Biol.* 151, 1799–1812. doi:10.1007/s00227-007-
371 0609-0

372 Fallon, E.K., Petersen, S., Brooker, R.A., Scott, T.B., 2017. Oxidative dissolution of
373 hydrothermal mixed-sulphide ore: An assessment of current knowledge in
374 relation to seafloor massive sulphide mining. *Ore Geol. Rev.* 86, 309–337.
375 doi:10.1016/j.oregeorev.2017.02.028

376 Freitas, E.C., Rocha, O., 2014. Acute and chronic toxicity of chromium and cadmium
377 to the tropical cladoceran *Pseudosida ramosa* and the implications for
378 ecotoxicological studies. *Environ. Toxicol.* 29, 176–186. doi:10.1002/tox.20784

379 Gaetke, L.M., Chow, C.K., 2003. Copper toxicity, oxidative stress, and antioxidant
380 nutrients. *Toxicology, Environmental and Nutritional Interactions Antioxidant*
381 *Nutrients and Environmental Health, Part C* 189, 147–163.
382 doi:10.1016/S0300-483X(03)00159-8

383 Gollner, S., Kaiser, S., Menzel, L., Jones, D.O.B., Brown, A., Mestre, N.C., van
384 Oevelen, D., Menot, L., Colaço, A., Canals, M., Cuvelier, D., Durden, J.M.,
385 Gebruk, A., Egho, G.A., Haeckel, M., Marcon, Y., Mevenkamp, L., Morato, T.,
386 Pham, C.K., Purser, A., Sanchez-Vidal, A., Vanreusel, A., Vink, A., Arbizu,
387 P.M., 2017. Resilience of benthic deep-sea fauna to mining activities. *Mar.*
388 *Environ. Res.* doi:10.1016/j.marenvres.2017.04.010

389 Gyedu-Ababio, T.K., Baird, D., 2006. Response of meiofauna and nematode
390 communities to increased levels of contaminants in a laboratory microcosm
391 experiment. *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 63, 443–450.

392 Hein, J.R., Mizell, K., Koschinsky, A., Conrad, T.A., 2013. Deep-ocean mineral
393 deposits as a source of critical metals for high- and green-technology
394 applications: Comparison with land-based resources. *Ore Geol. Rev.* 51, 1–
395 14. doi:10.1016/j.oregeorev.2012.12.001

396 Howell, R., 1983. Heavy metals in marine nematodes: uptake, tissue distribution and
397 loss of copper and zinc. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 14, 263–268.

398 Karlin, K.D., Tyeklár, Z., 2012. *Bioinorganic chemistry of copper*. Springer Science &
399 Business Media.

400 Kennedy, A.D., Jacoby, C.A., 1999. Biological indicators of marine environmental
401 health: meiofauna—a neglected benthic component? *Environ. Monit. Assess.*
402 54, 47–68.

403 Knight, R., Roberts, S., 2016. Initial results of batch reactor experiments to determine
404 sulphide oxidation rates and trace metal release under seafloor conditions.
405 *Appl. Earth Sci.* 125, 88–89. doi:10.1080/03717453.2016.1166645

- 406 Koschinsky, A., Fritsche, U., Winkler, A., 2001a. Sequential leaching of Peru Basin
407 surface sediment for the assessment of aged and fresh heavy metal
408 associations and mobility. *Deep Sea Res. Part II Top. Stud. Oceanogr.*,
409 Environmental Impact Studies for the Mining of Polymetallic Nodules from the
410 Deep Sea 48, 3683–3699. doi:10.1016/S0967-0645(01)00062-5
- 411 Koschinsky, A., Gaye-Haake, B., Arndt, C., Maue, G., Spitzzy, A., Winkler, A.,
412 Halbach, P., 2001b. Experiments on the influence of sediment disturbances on
413 the biogeochemistry of the deep-sea environment. *Deep Sea Res. Part II Top.*
414 *Stud. Oceanogr.*, Environmental Impact Studies for the Mining of Polymetallic
415 Nodules from the Deep Sea 48, 3629–3651. doi:10.1016/S0967-
416 0645(01)00060-1
- 417 Kwok, K.W.H., Leung, K.M.Y., Bao, V.W.W., Lee, J.-S., 2008. Copper toxicity in the
418 marine copepod *Tigropus japonicus*: Low variability and high reproducibility of
419 repeated acute and life-cycle tests. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.*, 5th International
420 Conference on Marine Pollution and Ecotoxicology 57, 632–636.
421 doi:10.1016/j.marpolbul.2008.03.026
- 422 Mertz, W., 1981. The essential trace elements. *Science* 213, 1332–1338.
423 doi:10.1126/science.7022654
- 424 Mestre, N.C., Brown, A., Thatje, S., 2013. Temperature and pressure tolerance of
425 larvae of *Crepidula fornicata* suggest thermal limitation of bathymetric range.
426 *Mar. Biol.* 160, 743–750.
- 427 Mestre, N.C., Calado, R., Soares, A.M., 2014. Exploitation of deep-sea resources:
428 The urgent need to understand the role of high pressure in the toxicity of
429 chemical pollutants to deep-sea organisms. *Environ. Pollut.* 185, 369–371.
- 430 Mestre, N.C., Thatje, S., Tyler, P.A., 2009. The ocean is not deep enough: pressure
431 tolerances during early ontogeny of the blue mussel *Mytilus edulis*. *Proc. R.*
432 *Soc. Lond. B Biol. Sci.* 276, 717–726.
- 433 Moens, T., Braeckman, U., Derycke, S., Fonseca, G., Gallucci, F., Ingels, J., Leduc,
434 D., Vanaverbeke, J., Van Colen, C., Vanreusel, A., Vincx, M., 2013. Ecology of
435 free-living marine nematodes, in: Schmidt-Rhaesa, A. (Ed.), *Handbook of*
436 *Zoology : Gastrotricha, Cycloneuralia and Gnathifera*, Vol. 2 : Nematoda. De
437 Gruyter, pp. 109–152.
- 438 Moens, T., Vincx, M., 1998. On the cultivation of free-living marine and estuarine
439 nematodes. *Helgoländer Meeresunters.* 52, 115–139.
440 doi:10.1007/BF02908742
- 441 Nelder, J.A., Wedderburn, R.W.M., 1972. Generalized linear models. *J. R. Stat. Soc.*
442 *Ser. Gen.* 135, 370–384. doi:10.2307/2344614
- 443 New, P., Brown, A., Oliphant, A., Burchell, P., Smith, A., Thatje, S., 2014. The effects
444 of temperature and pressure acclimation on the temperature and pressure
445 tolerance of the shallow-water shrimp *Palaemonetes varians*. *Mar. Biol.* 161,
446 697–709.
- 447 Ott, J., Schiemer, F., 1973. Respiration and anaerobiosis of free living nematodes
448 from marine and limnic sediments. *Neth. J. Sea Res.* 7, 233–243.
449 doi:10.1016/0077-7579(73)90047-1
- 450 Pempkowiak, J., Sikora, A., Biernacka, E., 1999. Speciation of heavy metals in
451 marine sediments vs their bioaccumulation by mussels. *Chemosphere, Matter*
452 *and Energy Fluxes in the Anthropocentric Environment* 39, 313–321.
453 doi:10.1016/S0045-6535(99)00112-5
- 454 Petersen, S., Krätschell, A., Augustin, N., Jamieson, J., Hein, J.R., Hannington, M.D.,
455 2016. News from the seabed – Geological characteristics and resource

456 potential of deep-sea mineral resources. *Mar. Policy* 70, 175–187.
457 doi:10.1016/j.marpol.2016.03.012

458 Pörtner, H.O., 2002. Climate variations and the physiological basis of temperature
459 dependent biogeography: systemic to molecular hierarchy of thermal tolerance
460 in animals. *Comp. Biochem. Physiol. A. Mol. Integr. Physiol.* 132, 739–761.
461 doi:10.1016/S1095-6433(02)00045-4

462 Pradillon, F., Gaill, F., 2007. Pressure and life: some biological strategies. *Rev.*
463 *Environ. Sci. Biotechnol.* 6, 181–195.

464 Proctor, A., Wotherspoon, S., 2015. LC50: Estimate LC50 in the presence of
465 additional stressors, R package version 0.1.1.

466 Proctor, A.H., King, C.K., Holan, J.R., Wotherspoon, S.J., 2017. Integrated modelling
467 of survival data from multiple stressor ecotoxicology experiments. *Environ. Sci.*
468 *Technol.* doi:10.1021/acs.est.7b02255

469 R Core Team, 2013. R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R
470 Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria.

471 Ritz, C., Baty, F., Streibig, J.C., Gerhard, D., 2015. Dose-response analysis using R.
472 *PLOS ONE* 10, e0146021. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0146021

473 RStudio Team, 2015. RStudio: Integrated development for R. RStudio, Inc., Boston,
474 MA.

475 Sávolgy, Z., Nagy, P., Varga, G., Havancsák, K., Hrács, K., Zárny, G., 2013. A novel
476 method for investigation of uptake and distribution of polluting microelements
477 and nanoparticles in soil-inhabiting nematodes. *Microchem. J.* 110, 558–567.
478 doi:10.1016/j.microc.2013.07.007

479 Scheiber, I., Dringen, R., Mercer, J.F.B., 2013. Copper: Effects of deficiency and
480 overload, in: Sigel, A., Sigel, H., Sigel, R.K.O. (Eds.), *Interrelations between*
481 *Essential Metal Ions and Human Diseases, Metal Ions in Life Sciences.*
482 Springer Netherlands, pp. 359–387. doi:10.1007/978-94-007-7500-8_11

483 Simpson, S.L., Spadaro, D.A., 2016. Bioavailability and chronic toxicity of metal
484 sulfide minerals to benthic marine invertebrates: Implications for deep-sea
485 exploration, mining and tailings disposal. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 50, 4061–
486 4070. doi:10.1021/acs.est.6b00203

487 Smith, C.R., De Leo, F.C., Bernardino, A.F., Sweetman, A.K., Arbizu, P.M., 2008.
488 Abyssal food limitation, ecosystem structure and climate change. *Trends Ecol.*
489 *Evol.* 23, 518–528. doi:10.1016/j.tree.2008.05.002

490 Smith, K.E., Brown, A., Thatje, S., 2015. The metabolic cost of developing under
491 hydrostatic pressure: experimental evidence supports macroecological
492 pattern. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 524, 71–82.

493 Sokolova, I.M., Frederich, M., Bagwe, R., Lannig, G., Sukhotin, A.A., 2012. Energy
494 homeostasis as an integrative tool for assessing limits of environmental stress
495 tolerance in aquatic invertebrates. *Marine Environmental Research* 79, 1–15.
496 doi:10.1016/j.marenvres.2012.04.003

497 Sokolova, I.M., Lannig, G., 2008. Interactive effects of metal pollution and
498 temperature on metabolism in aquatic ectotherms: implications of global
499 climate change. *Clim. Res.* 37, 181–201.

500 Somero, G.N., 2003. Protein adaptations to temperature and pressure:
501 complementary roles of adaptive changes in amino acid sequence and
502 internal milieu. *Comp. Biochem. Physiol. B Biochem. Mol. Biol.* 136, 577–591.
503 doi:10.1016/S1096-4959(03)00215-X

504 Song, S., Zhang, X., Wu, H., Han, Y., Zhang, J., Ma, E., Guo, Y., 2014. Molecular
505 basis for antioxidant enzymes in mediating copper detoxification in the

506 nematode *Caenorhabditis elegans*. PLOS ONE 9, e107685.
507 doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0107685

508 Sterk, R., Stein, J.K., 2015. Seabed mineral resources: A review of current mineral
509 resources and future developments. Deep Sea Mining Summit. Aberdeen,
510 Scotland.

511 Tchesunov, A.V., Portnova, D.A., Van Campenhout, J., 2014. Description of two free-
512 living nematode species of *Halomonhystera disjuncta* complex (Nematoda:
513 Monhysterida) from two peculiar habitats in the sea. Helgol. Mar. Res. 1–29.
514 doi:10.1007/s10152-014-0416-1

515 Thiel, H., 2001. Evaluation of the environmental consequences of polymetallic nodule
516 mining based on the results of the TUSCH Research Association. Deep Sea
517 Res. Part II Top. Stud. Oceanogr., Environmental Impact Studies for the
518 Mining of Polymetallic Nodules from the Deep Sea 48, 3433–3452.
519 doi:10.1016/S0967-0645(01)00051-0

520 Van Campenhout, J., Derycke, S., Moens, T., Vanreusel, A., 2014. Differences in life-
521 histories refute ecological equivalence of cryptic species and provide clues to
522 the origin of bathyal *Halomonhystera* (Nematoda). PLoS ONE 9, e111889.
523 doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0111889

524 Van Campenhout, J., Derycke, S., Tchesunov, A., Portnova, D., Vanreusel, A., 2013.
525 The *Halomonhystera disjuncta* population is homogeneous across the Håkon
526 Mosby mud volcano (Barents Sea) but is genetically differentiated from its
527 shallow-water relatives. J. Zool. Syst. Evol. Res. 52, 203–216.
528 doi:10.1111/jzs.12054

529 Van Campenhout, J., Vanreusel, A., Van Belleghem, S., Derycke, S., 2015.
530 Transcription, signaling receptor activity, oxidative phosphorylation, and fatty
531 acid metabolism mediate the presence of closely related species in distinct
532 intertidal and cold-seep habitats. Genome Biol. Evol. 8, 51–69.
533 doi:10.1093/gbe/evv242

534 Van Gaever, S., Moodley, L., De Beer, D., Vanreusel, A., 2006. Meiobenthos at the
535 Arctic Håkon Mosby Mud Volcano with a parental caring nematode thriving in
536 sulphide-rich sediments. Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser. 321.

537 Vanreusel, A., Hilario, A., Ribeiro, P.A., Menot, L., Arbizu, P.M., 2016. Threatened by
538 mining, polymetallic nodules are required to preserve abyssal epifauna. Sci.
539 Rep. 6, 26808. doi:10.1038/srep26808

540 Vranken, G., Brussel, D. van, Vanderhaeghen, R., Heip, C.H.R., 1984. The toxicity of
541 mercury on the free-living marine nematode *Monhystera disjuncta* Bastian,
542 1865. Ecotoxicological Test. Mar. Environ. 2.

543 Vranken, G., Heip, C., 1986. Toxicity of copper, mercury and lead to a marine
544 nematode. Mar. Pollut. Bull. 17, 453–457. doi:10.1016/0025-326X(86)90834-9

545 Vranken, G., Tiré, C., Heip, C., 1989. Effect of temperature and food on hexavalent
546 chromium toxicity to the marine nematode *Monhystera disjuncta*. Mar.
547 Environ. Res. 27, 127–136.

548 Vranken, G., Tire, C., Heip, C., 1988. The toxicity of paired metal mixtures to the
549 nematode *Monhystera disjuncta* (Bastian, 1865). Mar. Environ. Res. 26, 161–
550 179. doi:10.1016/0141-1136(88)90025-6

551 Vranken, G., Vanderhaeghen, R., Heip, C.H.R., 1985. Toxicity of cadmium to free-
552 living marine and brackish water nematodes (*Monhystera microphthalma*,
553 *Monhystera disjuncta*, *Pellioditis marina*). Dis. Aquat. Organ. 1.

554 Wedding, L.M., Reiter, S.M., Smith, C.R., Gjerde, K.M., Kittinger, J.N., Friedlander,
555 A.M., Gaines, S.D., Clark, M.R., Thurnherr, A.M., Hardy, S.M., Crowder, L.B.,

556 2015. Managing mining of the deep seabed. *Science* 349, 144–145.
557 doi:10.1126/science.aac6647
558 Wieser, W., Ott, J., Schiemer, F., Gnaiger, E., 1974. An ecophysiological study of
559 some meiofauna species inhabiting a sandy beach at Bermuda. *Mar. Biol.* 26,
560 235–248. doi:10.1007/BF00389254
561 Yancey, P.H., Rhea, M.D., Kemp, K., Bailey, D.M., 2004. Trimethylamine oxide,
562 betaine and other osmolytes in deep-sea animals: depth trends and effects on
563 enzymes under hydrostatic pressure. *Cell. Mol. Biol.* 50, 371–376.
564